

SLA-MLO: Congestion-Aware SLA-Based Scheduling of Multiple Links in IEEE 802.11be

Suneel Kumar
i2CAT
Barcelona, Spain
suneel.kumar@i2cat.net

Eduard Garcia-Villegas
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
Barcelona, Spain
eduardo.garcia@upc.edu

Daniel Camps-Mur
i2CAT
Barcelona, Spain
daniel.camps@i2cat.net

Abstract—As technology advances and factories adopt the industry 4.0 paradigm, the demand for low latency and highly reliable wireless connectivity becomes more crucial than ever. To cater to these challenges multi-link operation (MLO) is a new feature introduced in IEEE 802.11be (Wi-Fi 7) that requires scheduling packets in a station across multiple Wi-Fi links. This paper proposes SLA-MLO, which is a novel MLO scheduler for industrial communications designed to manage per-flow Service Level Agreement (SLA), where an SLA is defined as a maximum allowed percentile latency. We evaluate SLA-MLO by means of NS-3 packet-level simulations and compare it against a state-of-the-art MLO mechanism that schedules packets based on instantaneous per-link congestion measurements. Our results show that SLA-MLO achieves an average reduction in SLA deviation of 50%.

Index Terms—SLA-Deviation, Multi-link, Scheduling

I. INTRODUCTION

The requirements for low latency and high reliability are critical in smart factory environments, including mobile robots and closed-loop control systems, as well as for various real-time applications in fog/edge computing. In response, industry and academia are proposing different features for Wi-Fi 7 (IEEE 802.11be [1]), which will be further evolved in Wi-Fi 8 (IEEE 802.11bn [2]).

The IEEE P802.11 WG has previously introduced several enhancements to improve the performance of Wi-Fi WLANs, which included: i) increasing the raw PHY rate by enabling wider channel widths, ii) using more aggressive modulation and coding schemes (MCS), iii) supporting a larger number of multiple input multiple output (MIMO) spatial streams, and iv) enhancing efficiency by defining new channel access schemes such as OFDMA and MU-MIMO. IEEE 802.11be continues such evolution by allowing up to 320 MHz channels, 4096-QAM and increasing the number of spatial streams to 16, which is also aligned with the goal of supporting higher throughput and lower latencies. However, the most relevant new feature in IEEE 802.11be to enhance reliability and reduce latency in industrial environments is the multilink operation (MLO).

MLO enables a device to transmit and receive on multiple links simultaneously using different channels (possibly in different frequency bands) [1]. MLO defines two modes of operation. First, the simultaneous transmission and reception (STR) or asynchronous mode, in which transmission and re-

ception of packets in different links can occur simultaneously, if inter-device interference is properly treated. Second, the Non-STR or synchronous mode, which allows either reception or transmission at a given time. STR is expected to be implemented in access point (AP) type devices, whereas more constrained devices, such as smartphones, are expected to support the Non-STR mode.

Different techniques to implement MLO scheduling in IEEE 802.11be have been proposed that can be grouped into two categories. First, works like [3] propose protocol-level modifications such as changing EDCA parameters. This involves uniform device distribution among available links, a separate access category allocation for time-sensitive traffic, and specific parameter adjustments to prioritize access for real-time application stations (STAs). Second, algorithm-based approaches, which operate at the MAC Packet Data Unit (MPDU) scheduling level. Those algorithms can be static if their policies are fixed and do not adjust to the network conditions, such as packet duplication (PD) [4], load balancing (LB) [4], packet splitting (PS) [4], or defining dedicated channels for time-critical data [3]. These algorithms can be considered as dynamic, when link-selection policies are adapted using local information available at the device, or using global (network-wide) information. An example of a dynamic approach is the least congestion control (LCC) mechanism described in [5], [6], which balances load across links on the basis of the congestion measured in each link. Author in [4] also proposes a hybrid approach, which is a combination of PD, LB, and PS based on local information.

Despite its potential, there is a gap in the literature regarding the practical application of IEEE 802.11be's MLO in industrial and factory-like scenarios. In these environments, we can assume STR-capable devices connecting robots or production lines, where each MLO STA transports multiple flows with varying SLAs. In industrial communications, SLAs are usually defined as a maximum per-flow latency related to the specific manufacturing process that originates the flow. For instance, a collaborative robot may require a tight delay bound of 5 ms [7], while a human-machine interface (H2M) may have a relaxed delay bound of 50-200 ms [8]. Therefore, a novel approach is required to accommodate the specific demands posed by various traffic flows.

Our main contribution in this paper is the design and

evaluation of a novel MLO scheduler called SLA-based MLO (SLA-MLO), which, to the best of our knowledge, is the first one to explicitly consider per-flow SLA definitions in its scheduling decisions. SLA-MLO can be classified as a dynamic STR-based algorithm, which leverages locally available measurements, such as per-flow and per-packet delays. SLA-MLO is implemented in the NS-3 packet-level simulator which we use to benchmark its performance against other approaches found in the literature. We find that SLA-MLO achieves an average improvement of 50% in SLA deviation in scenarios considering a set of heterogeneous traffic flows.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the design of SLA-MLO. Section III presents our evaluation based on packet-level simulations. Finally, Section IV summarizes and concludes the paper.

II. DESIGN OF SLA-MLO

A. System Model

Figure 1 depicts the system model for SLA-MLO, which is implemented in the blue multi-link station (MLD-STAs) transmitting a set F of different flows (each flow $f \in \mathbf{F}$ having its own SLA) to an MLO-capable AP over the set \mathbf{L} of available links. Other stations, shown in gray, represent single-link non-MLD STAs sending background traffic.

The lower part of Figure 1 depicts the internal architecture of an MLD device. The process starts when MLD STA's MAC receives packets from the upper layers. Those packets are then classified according to the flow $f \in \mathbf{F}$ they belong to. Based on the SLA for that flow, the scheduler forwards the packet to link $i \in \mathbf{L}$ according to a probability $P_{f,i}$. The job of SLA-MLO is to determine $P_{f,i}$ for each flow and link in a dynamic and adaptive way.

Notice that all MLD STAs in Figure 1 are assumed to be STR capable, hence CSMA/CA rules are applied to all their links independently.

Fig. 1: System Model: Two SLA flows sent from MLD-STAs (STA1 and STA4) operating on link 1 and link 2. All other STAs are non-MLD.

B. SLA definition

In industrial applications, the timing of data and control signal flows is often synchronized with the cycle time of the

manufacturing process. Thus, latency is a critical factor that affects the performance and efficiency of the process. Cycle times can vary widely, from less than 1 ms for field bus communications to several hundred milliseconds for controllers to the edge communication [8].

Defining SLAs exclusively in terms of strict delay bounds, is not practical in unlicensed and contention-based access technologies such as Wi-Fi, where interference is hard to control even in industrial environments. Therefore, we adopt a more flexible notion of SLA based on the triple $(D_TH_f, Error_TH_f, T_{SLA})$, where:

- i. D_TH_f : maximum allowed delay from the moment a packet from flow f is received from the ingress queue until it is successfully acknowledged (c.f. Figure 1).
- ii. $Error_TH_f$: percentage of packets of flow f that are allowed to exceed D_TH_f .
- iii. T_{SLA} : duration of a running time window within which the percentage of packets of flow f exceeding D_TH_f has to be kept below $Error_TH_f$.

Based on this definition of SLA, we can assess the level of SLA compliance of a flow in the following way. First, a MLD STA measures the percentage of packets with a delay above D_TH_f for each flow f every t_sample , resulting in a time varying signal $Error_f(t)$. To check whether this error signal is compliant with the SLA, we first compute the moving average of $Error_f(t)$ within a window of duration T_{SLA} , which can be computed using a convolution operation:

$$Avg_error_f(t) = Error_f(t) * \left(\frac{1}{T_{SLA}} \right) Sq(t) \quad (1)$$

Where $Sq(t)$ is a square signal of duration T_{SLA} seconds. Then, the SLA deviation for flow f can be derived in the following way:

$$SLA_dev_f(t) = \max(Avg_error_f(t) - Error_TH_f, 0) \quad (2)$$

Note that $SLA_dev_f(t)$ is only increased when flow f exceeds its SLA's error threshold and is not decreased when the flow stays below the error, as this does not bring gains from the application perspective. Finally, the average SLA deviation across all flows is obtained as $\frac{1}{|\mathbf{F}|} \sum_{f \in \mathbf{F}} SLA_dev_f(t)$.

We will use this average SLA deviation to evaluate the performance of SLA-MLO in Section III.

C. Scheduler design

Algorithm 1 depicts the operation of the scheduler at one MLD-STAs for a flow f . SLA-MLO applies the same logic to all this STA's flows independently, according to their SLA.

Input parameters for the algorithm include the SLA definition for flow f , $(D_TH_f, Error_TH_f, T_{SLA})$. Then, SLA-MLO maintains the following internal variables for each flow:

- i. STA_Delay_f , delay of the last successfully transmitted packet of flow f . That is, the complete round trip time, which comprises the queuing delay, medium access delay, packet transmission time, and reception of corresponding acknowledgment.
- ii. $Delay_{f,i}$, representing the instantaneous delay of the last successfully transmitted packet of flow f through the link i .
- iii. $AvgDelay_Link_{f,i}$, an EWMA average of $Delay_{f,i}$.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for the SLA-MLO scheduler. Decision at an MLD station(STA) for flow f .

```

1: procedure 1: UPON RECEIVING ACK
2:   Get Ack of the last successful packet
3:   Measure  $STA\_Delay_f$  &  $Delay_{f,i}$ 
4:    $AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i} \leftarrow AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i} \cdot \alpha$ 
5:      $+ Delay_{f,i} \cdot (1 - \alpha)$ 
6:   if  $STA\_Delay_f \leq D\_TH_f$  then
7:      $SLA\_Followed \leftarrow SLA\_Followed + 1$ 
8:   else
9:      $SLA\_NotFollowed \leftarrow SLA\_NotFollowed + 1$ 
10:  end if
11:   $SLA\_Breach_f \leftarrow \frac{SLA\_NotFollowed}{SLA\_Followed + SLA\_NotFollowed}$ 
12: end procedure
13: procedure 2: CALCULATE PROBABILITY
14:   $L_{below} \leftarrow \{i \in L | Delay_{f,i} < D\_TH_f\}$ 
15:   $L_{above} \leftarrow \{i \in L | Delay_{f,i} \geq D\_TH_f\}$ 
16:  if  $SLA\_Breach_f \leq Error\_TH_f$  then
17:     $P_{f,i} \leftarrow \frac{1}{|L|}$ 
18:  else if  $|L_{below}| \neq 0$  then
19:     $P_{f,(i|i \in L_{above})} \leftarrow 0$ 
20:     $P_{f,(i|i \in L_{below})} \leftarrow \frac{1}{|L_{below}|}$ 
21:  else
22:     $P_{f,(i|i \in L)} \leftarrow \frac{1/AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i}}{\sum_{i \in L} 1/AvgDelay\_Link_{f,i}}$ 
23:  end if
24: end procedure
25:
26: procedure MAIN SCHEDULER LOOP
27:  while true do
28:    Wait for packet assigned to flow  $f$ 
29:     $P_{f,i} \leftarrow CalculateProbability()$ 
30:     $Rn \leftarrow uniform(0, 1)$ 
31:     $prob \leftarrow 0$ 
32:    for  $i \in L$  do
33:       $prob \leftarrow prob + P_{f,i}$ 
34:      if  $Rn < prob$  then
35:        forward the packet to link  $i$ 
36:      end if
37:    end for
38:  end while
39: end procedure

```

- iv. SLA_Breach_f , measuring the portion of packets having delay above the D_TH_f .

The output of the SLA-MLO algorithm are the probabilities of transmitting the next packet on the link i for flow f , i.e. $P_{f,i}$.

The algorithm starts from the procedure *Main Scheduler Loop* (line 26), when a packet is generated by flow f at MLD-STA. Before inserting a packet into the respective link's queue, the probability for each link is calculated using procedure 2 (line 13). Probability calculation involves the calculation of SLA_Breach_f of a flow, using procedure 1 (line 1). Thus, to calculate SLA breach, the delay at STA (both STA_Delay_f and $Delay_{f,i}$) is measured first. Those delays are updated when the acknowledgment of the last transmitted packet is received. The average link delay is calculated using an EWMA filter with $\alpha = 0.8$ (line 4). Two variables, namely $SLA_NotFollowed$ and $SLA_Followed$ are updated based on whether packets adhere to the delay limit D_TH_f to calculate the SLA breach (line 10). Procedure 2 is called (line 29) to obtain $P_{f,i}$ probabilities.

This calculation depends on the following two states:

State 1: if SLA breach is below $Error_TH_f$, then all links are assigned the same probability regardless of their delay. This allows the flow to use links with high delay, leaving resources in faster links for more constrained flows (line 16).

State 2: if SLA breach is above $Error_TH_f$ then two cases are considered (lines 18 to 22).

- **Case 1:** if one or more links have a delay lower than D_TH_f , then those links will be assigned equal probabilities. The rest of the links are discarded by setting their probability to 0, (lines 19 to 20).
- **Case 2:** if none of the links has a delay lower than D_TH_f , then their probability is inversely proportional to the average delay experienced by that link (line 22).

After calculating probabilities, the algorithm returns to the main procedure (line 29) and generates a uniformly distributed random number between 0 and 1. For each link, the probability is added to a cumulative probability variable. If the random number generated is less than the cumulative probability value, the packet is forwarded to that link's outbound queue (lines 32 to 37). Using this process, links with higher probability will have higher chances of being selected.

To summarize the behavior of the algorithm, we can consider a state, in which the network is experiencing a low congestion level, thus allowing a specific flow to comply with its SLAs, and traffic is distributed evenly across all links. In a second state, in which the SLA cannot be met, the scheduler chooses those links that can still adhere to the delay limits and prioritize them over other links. If the condition of the network degrades and no available links offer an acceptable delay, then the scheduler will attempt to distribute the traffic among the links based on their congestion levels.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To evaluate SLA-MLO, we use the NS-3 V.3.36 packet-level simulator, which we extend to support STR multi-link capabilities and to implement the SLA-MLO scheduler described in Section II. We have modified the NS-3 code to allow a device (WifiNetDevice) to be connected to multiple MAC objects (STAWifiMAC or APWifiMAC), each of which can install an independent PHY object. Then, packets received from upper layers at the higher MAC, are assigned to a flow by inspecting layer 2 or 3 information of the packet. The scheduler code keeps track of the needed metrics (cf. section II), assigns each packet to a link, and forwards it to the corresponding lower MAC transmission queue.

For our simulation, we have chosen the 5 and 6 GHz bands because it is expected to be less interfered and are, therefore, more likely to be used in industrial scenarios. Typical industrial setups feature controlled APs on non-overlapping channels, minimizing inter-BSS interference. Hence, we prioritize single BSS evaluation. We base our simulations on a two-link MLO since it is the most probable configuration for the first wave of Wi-Fi 7 MLD STAs that will benefit from multiple channels while minimizing cost. We leave for future work the evaluation of SLA-MLO with more than two links. Table I summarizes the essential simulation parameters, used throughout the paper, unless otherwise specified. Simulated scenarios follow the system model depicted in Figure 1, that is, one MLD AP serves a number of MLD STAs over two links, and a number of non-MLD STAs are connected to the same AP through one link or the other. MLD STAs generate SLA flows, while non-MLD STAs generate background UDP traffic. For all setups in this paper, nodes are randomly deployed within a 15-meter range from AP.

We divide our performance evaluation in three different experiments. First, we setup a controlled scenario that allows us to validate the dynamics of SLA-MLO. Second, we benchmark SLA-MLO against a representative approach in the state of the art, under controlled scenarios where we vary the background load in each link and the heterogeneity between SLA flows. Third, we benchmark

Fig. 2: SLA-MLO scheduler in different states/cases. For 1-10s no background traffic is present. For 10 to 20s only link 1 carries background traffic and for 21 to 30s background traffic is present in both links. For 31 to 40s background traffic is only on link 1

SLA-MLO in a realistic industrial scenario with random background interference on each link.

TABLE I: Overview of General simulation parameters

Feature	Simulation Parameter
Frequency Band	6GHz (channel number 15 & 47)
Channel Width	160MHz
Standard	IEEE 802.11ax
Aggregation Mode	OFF
MCS	11
Rate adaptation	Constant Rate Wi-Fi
Payload Size	700B
Simulation time	20s (per simulation)
Packet Queue size	500p (per link)
Traffic Type	Uplink
Propagation model	Log Distance Propagation Loss Model

A. Proof of Concept

Simulation Setup: we evaluate how SLA-MLO behaves under different SLA breach conditions. Thus, we setup one SLA flow on one MLD station with a strict SLA consisting of $D_{TH_f} = 0.15$ ms, and $Error_{TH_f} = 5\%$. The SLA flow consists of uplink constant rate UDP traffic with an interarrival time of 1 ms and a packet size of 700 bytes. We study the dynamics of SLA-MLO in a 40 second simulation where background traffic varies as follows:

- i. Between 1s and 10s, there is no background traffic, and only the SLA flow is transmitted.
- ii. Between 11s and 20s, 8 non-MLD stations introduce background traffic at a packet arrival rate of 1.65 ms per STAs on link 1 and a packet size of 700 bytes.
- iii. Between 21 and 30s, 8 non-MLD STAs on each link generate background traffic at a packet arrival rate of 1.65 ms per station and a packet size of 700 bytes.
- iv. Between 31s and 40s case ii) is repeated.

Figure 2 depicts the evolution over time of three internal SLA-MLO variables defined in section II-C i.e. link probability ($P_{f,i}$), SLA breach (SLA_{Breach_f}), and instantaneous per-link delay ($Delay_{f,i}$).

Discussion: during the first 10 seconds, in the absence of background traffic, both links provide delays below D_{TH_f} , and SLA-MLO distributes the same load through both links by assigning equal probabilities, as per Algorithm 1, line 16. From 10s to 20s, link 1 experiences an increased delay due to the presence of background traffic, while link 2 delay remains below D_{TH_f} . This results in an increased SLA breach, which the algorithm keeps around 5% ($Error_{TH_f}$) by favoring link 2. Note that the definition of $Error_{TH_f} > 0$ adds flexibility, allowing the scheduler to test link 1 occasionally (algorithm 1, line 18 to line 20). Between 20s and 30s, both links experience increased delays due to a similar background traffic, resulting in $SLA_{Breach_f} \geq 5\%$, with both links exceeding D_{TH_f} . Recall that using random-based access such as CSMA on a license-free band, QoS cannot be guaranteed in scenarios with many contending STAs offering a high load. In those cases, SLA-MLO starts assigning $P_{f,i}$ inversely proportional to the average delay of each link (algorithm 1, line 22). Between 30s and 40s, interference in link 2 is switched off, and SLA-MLO quickly returns to the situation where most of the traffic is forwarded through link 2. This experiment shows how acting on a per-packet basis, SLA-MLO is able to quickly adapt to changes in the environment that may impact time-critical flows.

B. Benchmarking SLA-MLO

Simulation Setup: a dynamic approach for congestion control, known as least congestion control (LCC) is proposed in [5]. This method keeps track of the congestion levels to select the least congested link. In [5], the authors suggest updating the scheduling decisions every second, but we implement LCC in NS-3 acting on a per-packet basis for a fair comparison with our SLA-MLO. Our goal

Fig. 3: SLA deviation of different flows- Upper side plots show SLA deviation for scenario 1,2 and 3, respectively. Downside plots show link distribution of flows (% of flow’s packets going through link 1).

TABLE II: Simulation parameters for benchmarking scenario

Scenario	Flow Number	SLA Breach threshold	Delay
1	1&3	8%	5 ms
	2	5%	0.25 ms
2	1, 3 & 4	8%	5 ms
	2	5%	0.25 ms
3	1, 3 to 6	8%	10 ms
	2	5%	1 ms

is to understand how SLA-MLO compares to LCC when focusing on SLA compliance.

We simulate three different scenarios that are described in Table II. Across all three scenarios, the number of SLA flows increases, while link 1 consistently exhibits higher load than link 2. Notably, there is a consistent asymmetry in the background load between link 1 and 2 in scenarios 1 and 2 (4:2 non-MLD STA on link 1 and 2), which becomes more pronounced in scenario 3 (8:2 non-MLD STA on link 1 and 2). Each SLA flow represents an MLD-STA that sends traffic to an MLD-AP. In all scenarios, the flow interarrival times are set up to operate close to the available channel capacity in order to see the effects of the schedulers being evaluated. In scenarios 1 and 2, the packet arrival rate for all SLA flows is 1.5 ms while, in scenario 3, it is set to 2.8 ms.

We evaluate SLA-MLO and LCC in terms of SLA deviation, as defined in section II-B. In addition, we look at the percentage of SLA flow packets going through one of the links to gain further insight into the behavior of each scheduler.

Discussion: Figure 3 compares the performance of SLA-MLO and LCC. The upper row shows SLA deviation when increasing the amount of background traffic. The lower row shows, for each experiment, the percentage of SLA flow packets through each link. In all scenarios, SLA-MLO outperforms LCC in terms of SLA deviation. The SLA deviation reduction ranges from approximately 5% to

60% when comparing the third quartile of the boxplot in scenarios 1 and 2, with the gain increasing as the background interference grows. In scenario 3, for low to medium loads the result is similar to scenarios 1 and 2. However, with a heavy load, there is no much space for a scheduler to guarantee an SLA under the rules of IEEE 802.11’s distributed random access. Nevertheless, our proposed scheduler clearly outperforms LCC.

To understand the reasons for the gains achieved by SLA-MLO when compared to LCC, we need to look at the flow to link allocation depicted in the lower row of Figure 3. In the figure, we see for LCC (solid) and for SLA-MLO (dashed) the percentage of packets forwarded through link 1 (the most congested one). We can see that, for LCC, all flows are biased towards link 2, because LCC greedily tries to transmit through the least congested link. SLA-MLO, however, treats differently the SLA flows depending on their requirements. SLA flows with more relaxed requirements are distributed through links 1 and 2, whereas the more constrained SLA flows favor the less congested link 2. Note that more relaxed flows can afford the additional delay incurred in link 1 without seeing their SLA affected, thus leaving more space in link 2 for the more constrained SLA flows. This is the reason behind the gains exhibited by SLA-MLO.

C. Industrial scenario

Simulation Setup: in an industrial or factory-like scenario, multiple machines with different traffic patterns and QoS requirements need to interact seamlessly to ensure smooth and efficient operations. Therefore, in order to evaluate the proposed scheduler’s efficacy within a realistic factory setting, where a variety of industrial flows and background traffic are present, we have chosen four industrial flows. Flows 1 and 2 represent motion control and closed-loop control traffic (through mobile-connected I/O gateways), as proposed in [9]. Flow 3 and Flow 4 mimic the traffic exchanged among collaborative robots, which include velocity and distance information [10]. Table

TABLE III: Simulation parameters in an industrial scenario

(a) Modified General parameters for simulation

Feature	Simulation Parameters
Frequency Band	6GHz & 5GHz
Channel Width	160MHz & 20MHz
Rate Control Algorithm	Minstrel
Flow1	Motion Control (64 B packet per 10ms) [9]
Flow2	Close loop Control (64 B packet per 1ms) [9]
Flow 3&4	Collaborative robots (20 B packet per 10ms) [10]
Background flow	Videos traffic (1500 B packet and packet arrival time varies from 1 ms to 2.4 ms) [9]

(b) Simulation parameters per flows

Flow Number	SLA Breach threshold	Delay
1	10%	10 ms
2	5%	1 ms
3 & 4	10%	5 ms ^a

^aSelected delay of 5ms motivated by [10], where 5ms delay caused 0.01m positioning error in robot coordination.

Fig. 4: Industrial scenario: deviation of flow 2 (with strict requirements) against increasing random background load.

III summarizes the most relevant parameters of the simulation. We selected different frequencies and bandwidths to emulate real-world conditions. 12 and 6 non-MLD STAs generate background traffic on links 1 and 2, respectively, with a fixed packet size. In real industrial scenarios, this background traffic can be periodic or aperiodic. Hence, we randomly assigned traffic on and off time, i.e. each background station will start and finish a background flow randomly, but at a fixed packet inter-arrival time. To ensure the statistical validity of our results, for each boxplot point, we conducted simulations using 10 different seeds.

Discussion: in Figure 4, the SLA deviation of flow 2 (the most stringent flow in the scenario) is depicted under varying background loads. Background load on both links is varied by changing the data rate for all Non-MLD STAs. By analyzing this worst-case scenario, we can confirm the overall effectiveness of SLA-MLO. The plot clearly shows that, on average, SLA-MLO outperforms LCC by 50% when comparing the third quantile of the boxplot. Logically SLA deviation of both schedulers tends to increase with the increase in background traffic. This is due to the fact that, higher traffic loads can lead to more contention for resources, which can negatively impact the flow’s overall performance. However, SLA-MLO consistently performs better than LCC, indicating that it is better equipped to handle such situations and maintain optimal performance levels. These results indicate that the proposed scheduler is well-suited for real industrial environments. Specifically, it can handle the stringent

requirements of such environments and maintain high levels of performance, making it a valuable tool for industry professionals.

IV. CONCLUSION

A congestion-aware scheduler for IEEE 802.11be MLD STAs has been proposed, which is expected to be especially useful in industrial scenarios where multiple flows with varying service level agreements (SLAs) exist in the network. This scheduler can switch links based on the network’s congestion level, as measured by the delay experienced by each traffic flow, while also adjusting traffic to accommodate stations (STAs) with strict SLAs alongside those with more flexible SLAs. The overall improvement in latency, in comparison to other approaches in the related literature, was presented by analyzing the SLA deviation metric.

Acknowledging that no strict QoS can be guaranteed with contention-based access on ISM bands, we showed how MLO improves delay metrics, but MLO alone may not be enough in some scenarios. In the future, we expect to evaluate this scheduler in combination with other mechanisms such as OFDMA or MU-MIMO.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is supported by the EU’s H2020 5GSmartFact project under the MSCA grant agreement ID 956670. This work was also partly supported by the Spanish the MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011050 through project PID2019-106808RA-I00 and MINECO and EU PRTR UNICO I+D number TSI-063000-2021-15-6GSMART-EZ.

REFERENCES

- [1] IEEE 802.11beTM/D1.5 Working Group, “Draft Standard for Information technology— Part 11: Wireless LAN Medium Access Control (MAC) and Physical Layer (PHY) Specifications Amendment 8: Enhancements for extremely high throughput (EHT),” tech. rep., IEEE-SA Standards Board, Mar 2022. Soc. London, vol. A247, pp. 529–551, April 1955.
- [2] L. Galati Giordano, G. Geraci, M. Carrascosa, and B. Bellalta, “What will wi-fi 8 be? a primer on ieee 802.11bn ultra high reliability,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.10442*, 2023.
- [3] D. V. Bankov, A. I. Lyakhov, E. M. Khorov, and K. S. Chemrov, “On the use of multilink access methods to support real-time applications in wi-fi networks,” *Journal of Communications Technology and Electronics*, vol. 66, pp. 1476–1484, 2021.
- [4] M.-T. Suer, C. Thein, H. Tchouankem, and L. Wolf, “Multi-connectivity as an enabler for reliable low latency communications—an overview,” *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 156–169, 2019.
- [5] A. Loópez-Raventoós and B. Bellalta, “IEEE 802.11be Multi-Link Operation: When the Best Could Be to Use Only a Single Interface,” in *2021 19th Mediterranean Communication and Computer Networking Conference (MedComNet)*, (Ibiza, Spain), pp. 1–7, IEEE, 2021.
- [6] A. López-Raventoós and B. Bellalta, “Dynamic traffic allocation in ieee 802.11be multi-link w lans,” *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 1404–1408, 2022.
- [7] S. M. Theres, C. Thein, H. Tchouankem, and L. Wolf, “Adaptive multi-connectivity scheduling for reliable low-latency communication in 802.11be,” in *2022 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, pp. 102–107, IEEE, 2022.
- [8] M. K. Atiq, R. Muzaffar, Ó. Seijo, I. Val, and H.-P. Bernhard, “When ieee 802.11 and 5g meet time-sensitive networking,” *IEEE Open Journal of the Industrial Electronics Society*, vol. 3, pp. 14–36, 2021.
- [9] P. M. Rost and T. Kolding, “Performance of integrated 3gpp 5g and ieee tsn networks,” *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 51–56, 2022.
- [10] S. Sudhakaran, V. Mageshkumar, A. Baxi, and D. Cavalcanti, “Enabling qos for collaborative robotics applications with wireless tsn,” in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)*, pp. 1–6, 2021.